

Milestone 27: Completion of 1st programme revision with WP4-6 recommendation

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ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

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1 Introduction

This document constitutes the “Completion of 1st programme revision with WP4-6 recommendation” a milestone (M27) of the ATMO-ACCESS project (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities). It represents the organized contribution of distributed atmospheric research facilities for developing a pilot for a new model of Integrating Activities. ATMO-ACCESS aims to develop a programme of access to several atmospheric Research Infrastructures individually or in combination. WP7 aims to integrate the various modalities of access and suggested pilots delivered by the other WPs into a programme of physical, remote, and virtual access. The programme will reflect the strategic development of access modalities to increasingly include an updated range of novel Transnational Access (TNA) calls. The purpose of this document is to present the revision of a new access programme that will be implemented for the ATMO-ACCESS calls. The programme was designed by WP7 members after consulting WP4-6 leaders and the organizing committee, while it has been ratified by the Strategic TNA/VA Access Board (STVB).

2 Outline timetable and programme

Considering the recommendations received by WP4-WP6, the outline timetable and schedule (Milestone 26) have been revised as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Revised timetable and programme for novel access rollout.

In the revised timetable, a sequential call-evaluation-selection-access scheme has been implemented. Each call will remain open for two months, followed by a two-month evaluation period. To ensure competitiveness and transparency, a selection meeting will take place at the end of each evaluation period and the selection committee (consisting of STVB, CO and SAMU members) will decide on the proposals that will be accepted.

A ranking system shall be implemented at the end of each meeting. The successful projects can be carried out within a complete year from the deadline of the particular call.

In line with the outline suggestion (milestone 26), three different types of activity modalities shall be included in the TNA programme: a. recurrent calls, b. continuous calls and c. work package-related pilots.

The recurrent calls will include 4 general calls (having as criterion the scientific excellence) and 3 specific calls that will have the following characteristics:

- a. Comply with EU's Green Deal objectives (call 2),
- b. Remote access (i.e. using facilities' equipment and infrastructure-specific tools) only (call 4), and
- c. Multi-disciplinary access with specific incentives (call 6) to encourage application to this call rather than the general calls. For this call, an increased financial support to the users (e.g., up to 10 k€ per proposal) is recommended.

In addition to the aforementioned calls, calibration and specific topic related calls will be announced and implemented on a bimonthly basis to run concurrently with the recurrent calls. To ensure competitiveness, these calls will be evaluated together with the recurrent calls during the selection meetings.

The continuous calls will be implemented from M19 (October 2022). They will target:

- a. A continuous fast track call with strict fast-track criteria for the evaluation of the proposals with sufficient justification of the reasons for the application under this call category.
- b. A continuous private sector call to satisfy the objectives of Task 6.3 (New access modality for technology pilots) using market-driven criteria and allowing the flexibility to provide industrial developments and novel products, with timely aligned objectives with private partners.
- c. A continuous Virtual Access (VA) call to satisfy the objectives of WP5 and 10 using non-competitive criteria. The VA calls are strictly related to the exploitation of data and products that a specific facility can offer, keeping the same unit cost regarding the reimbursement of the provider organization.

To provide quality assurance of the continuous calls, TNA proposals to these calls will be reviewed in the same evaluation periods (lightened in the respective continuous call bar in Table 1) and ranked alongside the other TNA proposals at the selection meetings of the recurrent calls. Since the continuous TNA cannot be retrospectively selected according to these rankings, they will solely be used to adjust the quality threshold for TNA support applied in future selection in the continuous calls.

The WP4 and WP6 pilots will aim new access modalities in the frames of Tasks 6.2 (New access modality for stakeholders) and 6.4 (new access modality for public authorities), as well as the AGORA training in the frames of WP4. The WP-related calls are considered as novel pilot TNAs where the stakeholders are the main users.

The overall goal of the outlined timetable (Table 1) is to explore various and novelty-related nodes of transnational access to atmospheric research infrastructures. The implementation of such diverse access schemes in the frames of ATMO-ACCESS shall set the base for facilitating continuity in providing effective and

sustainable access across European Research Infrastructures, maximizing the collaboration potentials and benefits from the use of each RI equipment.